

Application of IoT in Controlling Water Reservoirs

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Abstract – Controlling and monitoring of water tanks in the Lhokseumawe State Polytechnic ICT Building still experiences limitations regarding filling and monitoring in the tank. Water will continue to be filled in the tank and will indirectly result in the wastage of energy. Scheduled tank water filling system for ICT Buildings Using atmega 328 as a microcontroller that controls the entire system, Ultrasonic sensors measure water levels, relays as pump automation, and the esp8266 module is used to send data to android using the virtuino application. Monitoring the water level when filling the tank is expected to be one step in saving water and energy. Based on testing, the average delay of the response of the virtuino display using WiFi and sim card will calculate the delay on and off the pump. The alarm will turn on when the water level in the tendon has reached ≥ 100 cm. This alarm sound is sent through the virtuino application so that the user will get a warning when the water in the tank is full. This condition can be overcome by implementing the Internet of things (IoT) in the tank at the Lhokseumawe State Polytechnic ICT Building. The system to be built uses the Virtuino interface.

Keywords: Virtuino, Ultrasonic, Esp8266, Flow meters

Introduction

Every building, both offices, and campuses always needs water for daily activities, such as toilets, washing hands, cleaning, and so on. Currently, building construction is always equipped with water reservoirs to store water produced from boreholes or pumping wells to conserve water use. In addition, the use of reservoirs serves to check the total use of water each month [1]. Not only that, but it is also often there is a void in the tendon when water is used. This hinders activities that must be carried out immediately if the occupants of the building are in a hurry. In addition, the negligence of filling the reservoir water so that the water overflows is also a problem in buildings with more than two floors. If this happens frequently, it will result in wastage of water which will have an impact on increasing electricity costs because the pump will run frequently.

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a concept where an object can transfer data over a network without requiring human-to-human or human-to-computer interaction. IoT has evolved from the convergence of wireless technologies, micro-electromechanical systems (MEMS), and the Internet. "A Things" in the Internet of Things can be defined as a subject, for example a person with a heart implant monitor, a farm animal with a biochip transponder, a car that has built-in sensors to warn the driver when tire pressure is low. So far, IoT is most closely related to machine-to-machine (M2M) communications in manufacturing, power, oil, and gas. Products built with M2M communication capabilities are often referred to as smart systems or "smart" [2][3].

Figure 1. Water Reservoir Control System (a). PNL ICT Building and Water Reservoir; (b). Manual Reservoir Control, (c). IoT-Based Water Reservoir Control

Hence, the specific objectives of this research are the application of the Internet of Things (IoT) in controlling water reservoirs via the SCADA GUI. From this research, it is expected any innovation in the monitoring and controlling system of water reservoirs by applying computer technology, especially in the field of the Internet of Things. The research conducted focuses on the Information and Communication Technology research field with the research theme, namely ICT Infrastructure Development, with the topic of internet protocol (IP)-based telecommunications research and the Internet of things and the basic framework for PNL's flagship research roadmap, namely IoT Development for industrial, environmental management, health, transportation, and supply logistics.

Materials and Methods

MQTT is the OASIS standard for IoT connectivity. It is a publish/subscribe, very simple and lightweight messaging protocol, designed for constrained devices and low bandwidth, high latency, or unreliable networks. The design principle is to minimize network bandwidth and device resource requirements while also striving to ensure reliability and some level of delivery guarantee. These principles also turn out to make the protocol ideal for the "Internet of Things" world of connected devices, and for mobile applications where bandwidth and battery power are prohibitively expensive[14].

MQTT was invented by Dr Andy Stanford-Clark of IBM, and Arlen Nipper of Arcom (now Eurotech), in 1999. MQTT has been widely applied in various industries since 1999. MQTT is the OASIS standard. Specifications are managed by the OASIS MQTT Technical Committee. MQTT for Sensor Networks is intended for embedded devices on non-TCP/IP networks, such as Zigbee. MQTT-SN is a publish/subscribe message protocol for wireless sensor networks (WSN), with the aim of extending the MQTT protocol beyond the reach of the TCP/IP infrastructure for Sensor and Actuator solutions.

Virtuino is an Android application for monitoring sensors or controlling via local WIFI or internet. The Arduino/NodeMCU/ ESP8266 project, which we create visuals with widgets such as LEDs, buttons, switches, display values, instruments, regulators, etc. This application supports remote monitoring systems only by using internet media with the Thingspeak webserver, where in this application we can create an interface and analogs presented by this application. The application display can be seen in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Display Virtuino [7,11,12]

The stages of the research are generally described in a flowchart as shown in Figure 3 and the system block diagram is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Flowchart of Research Stages

In Figure 3, the first stage of the research is identification, namely looking directly at the problems that exist in the environment or in the field. Furthermore, in the second stage is the formulation of the problem, namely grouping the problems that have been identified. The next stage is the research method stage which is carried out to collect data from various sources, analyze the data and look for the right value in research. The next stage is entering into system design, namely making a picture or form of design that will be made. After the system design stage is complete, then proceed to the last stage, namely the system testing stage which is carried out to test the system that has been made.

Figure 4. System Block Diagram

The explanation of the block diagram is as follows:

1. Esp8266 is used to send data read by sensors to Android
2. Node MCU 8266 as controller of the entire system
3. Relay to connect and disconnect the current to the pump
4. Pump to fill water into the tank
5. JSN SR-04 (Ultrasonic) is used to detect the water level in the water tank
6. Android is used to send and receive data via MQTT
7. PC is used to send and receive data via MQTT

Figure 4 is a picture of the system block diagram design. The system will work when the water reservoir located at the top of the building on the 3rd floor will automatically fill if the sensor detects that the water in the reservoir is empty. The master will send sensor data to the slave then the water pump will automatically turn on. Once the sensor detects that the water reservoir is full, the pump will automatically turn off. The process of turning on and off the pump can be done remotely using the Virtuino application. On Android, the condition of the water level will be visible if it reaches 5 cm, which reminds us that the water in the reservoir is at the lowest level and vice versa, an alarm will sound if the level in the reservoir has approached a maximum of 40 cm.

The water tank research design with IoT is presented in Figure 5 below and a sensor used to measure the water level in the reservoir is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Design of Water Tank Research with IoT

Figure 6. Ultrasonic Sensor Design

The Node MCU 8266 series is a Wi-Fi module that functions as an additional device for a microcontroller such as an Arduino so that it can connect directly to Wi-Fi and create a TCP/IP connection. The Node MCU 8266 circuit can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 8. Relay Design

Results and Discussion

Testing is useful for measuring the reliability of systems or tools created from hardware to software. So that the expected results can be achieved well. Testing is carried out in several stages, starting from measuring the tools used to integrated testing.

Figure 9. IoT using NodeMCU 8266

Figure 10. Virtuino display

Table 1. Virtuino data transmission reading

No	Hot spot	Keystroke testing in virtuino	Delay (detik)
1	Oppo A16	Pump	5,28
		1st Floor Valve	5,28
		2nd Floor Valve	5,31
		3rd Floor V	5,67
2	Oppo A9	Pump	5,22
		1st Floor Valve	5,20
		2nd Floor Valve	5,26
		3rd Floor Valve	5,31
3	Lab. Robotics	Pump	3,50
		1st Floor Valve	3,50
		2nd Floor Valve	3,52
		3rd Floor Valve	3,53
4	Department of Electrical Engineering	Pump	3,82
		1st Floor Valve	3,86
		2nd Floor Valve	3,88
		3rd Floor Valve	3,89

The average response time for sending data on a Wi-Fi network is faster than the response time on a mobile cellular network, reaching 3.67 seconds. In this test, it can be seen that the Wi-Fi network is relatively faster and more stable with a smaller difference in response time on the same Wi-Fi network. Meanwhile, the response time for reading data on the mobile hotspot network will depend on the stability of the local 4G data network and the type of cellular operator used.

Testing was carried out to investigate the water level in the reservoir and monitor it on the Virtuino GUI display on the Android Smartphone device. The aim is to determine the performance of the Virtuino sensor and software in displaying real-time water level and flow data and animations on the Smartphone display as shown in Figure 10. Water level testing in the storage tank is carried out in 6 level conditions, namely levels 0%, 20%, 40%, 60%, 80%, and 100%. The data is shown in Table 2. The

prototype reservoir used in this case is a reservoir with a height of 45 cm, with a level of 0 cm as the 0% level, while the maximum height of the reservoir or 100% is referenced at 38 cm from the reservoir height limit as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Display on Tandon and Virtuno 50% Water Size

Figure 12. Display on Tandon and Virtuno 100% Water Level

The flowmeter sensor is used to detect the water discharge value coming out of the storage tank as presented in Figure 12. The flowmeter sensor used is the YF-S201 type with frequency output. Based on the flowmeter sensor datasheet, the following is a flowmeter sensor table based on the datasheet to determine the discharge at a certain frequency in Table 2.

Table 2. Flowmeter sensor discharge datasheet

Frekuensi	Debit
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(Hz)	(L/Min)
16	2
32,5	4
49,3	6
65,5	8
82	10
90,2	12

Based on Table 2, a graph of frequency versus discharge from the flowmeter sensor can be made. A graphic image can be seen in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Flowmeter sensor output graph based on datasheet

Flowmeter sensor measurements are carried out by measuring how quickly the water fills a measuring cup with a volume of 2.45 L using a stopwatch as presented in Figure 13. After getting the measurement time, then convert it to liters/minute. Based on these sensor tests, the test results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Flowmeter sensor test data

Frequency (Hz)	Waktu (detik)	Debit (L/Min)
70	17,1	8,6
60	19,5	7,5
50	24,4	6
40	30,2	4,8
30	38,1	3,9
20	59,1	2,5
10	97,3	1,5

Using Table 3, a graph of frequency versus discharge from the flowmeter sensor can be made. A graphic image of sensor testing can be seen in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Graph of flowmeter sensor output testing

Conclusion

Based on the research results, conclusions can be drawn including:

1. The use of a water level monitoring system with Internet of Things technology can provide faster information to system users, and the information obtained is more accurate than monitoring using conventional methods because you can monitor anywhere as long as the equipment is connected to the Internet.
2. Using the virtuino application is very useful in this monitoring system because the virtuino is the output as well as the server which is the communication medium between the device and the smartphone. The interface is very easy to use and easy for users to understand.

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